

Republic of the Philippines
CEBU TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY
Moalboal Campus

Poblacion West Moalboal, Cebu
Website: <http://www.ctu.edu.ph> E-mail: ctumoalboalcampus@gmail.com
Tel.Nos.: (032) 474-8196; 474-8104; 474-8383
Fax Nos.: 474-8196; 474-8104; 474-8383

**ASSESSMENT OF MUSCULOSKELETAL DISORDERS FOR JEEPNEY
DRIVERS; A CASE OF SOUTH CEBU**

An Undergraduate Thesis

Presented to

College of Engineering

CEBU TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY – MOALBOAL CAMPUS

Moalboal, Cebu

In Partial Fulfillment

of the Requirements for the Degree

BACHELOR OF SCIENCE IN INDUSTRIAL ENGINEERING

Submitted by:

BOLONGAITA, JUVY D.

GEMPEROSO, CHEVILYN ROSE G.

MILMAO, ROGIE Y.

REUMA, MESSIEH GRACE N.

ENGR. JIÑA MARIE R. MABANTO

Research Adviser

October 2024

This Undergraduate thesis entitled “**ASSESSMENT OF MUSCULOSKELETAL DISORDERS FOR JEEPNEY DRIVERS; A CASE OF SOUTH CEBU**”, prepared and submitted by **Juvy D. Bolongaita, Chevilyn Rose G. Gemperoso, Messieh Grace N. Reuma, Rogie Y. Milmao**, and in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree **BACHELOR OF SCIENCE IN INDUSTRIAL ENGINEERING (BSIE)**, has been examined and is recommended for acceptance and approval for **ORAL EXAMINATION**.

THESIS COMMITTEE

BENJAMIN D. RUBIN, PIE, MSIE

Chairman

JIÑA MARIE R. MABANTO, IE

Thesis Adviser

DANTE T. VALLENTE, IE, MA. Ed.

Member

THRECIA M. BARAZAN, IE

Member

MERRY JOSEPHINE C. BALICOCO, IE

Member

LIMIC M. DE LA CALZADA II, ECE, MSIT

Member

JESSIE REY F. AVENIDO, IE

Member

PANEL OF EXAMINERS

BENJAMIN D. RUBIN, PIE, MSIE

Chairman

JIÑA MARIE R. MABANTO, IE

Thesis Adviser

DANTE T. VALLENTE, IE, MA. Ed.

Member

THRECIA M. BARAZAN, IE

Member

MERRY JOSEPHINE C. BALICOCO, IE

Member

JESSIE REY F. AVENIDO, IE

Member

Accepted and approved in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of Bachelor of Science in Industrial Engineering.

CHARMAINE P. ANTECRISTO, Ph. D. TM

Campus Director

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The researchers would like to express their deepest gratitude to the following individuals for their invaluable support and contribution to the completion of this study:

First and foremost, we are immensely grateful to our research instructor, **Engr. Benjamin D. Rubin**, for his continuous guidance, unwavering support, and valuable insights throughout this research endeavor. His expertise, patience, and encouragement have been instrumental in shaping the direction of this study and enhancing its quality.

To **Engr. Jiña Marie R. Mabanto**, our thesis adviser, for her continuous guidance and support in making this research possible.

To our **Thesis Committee and Panel of Examiners** for accepting and approving our research study in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of Bachelor of Science in Industrial Engineering.

We would also like to extend our heartfelt appreciation to the **members** of this thesis, Juvy D. Bolongaita, Chevilyn Rose G. Gemperoso, Messieh Grace N. Reuma and Rogie Y. Milmao. Our constructive feedback, critical evaluation, and thoughtful suggestions have significantly enriched this work.

Our sincere thanks go to our **friends and classmates** for their support, stimulating discussions, and their extending of hands whenever confusions hit us in the process. Their friendship has provided much-needed motivation and a sense of belonging throughout this demanding journey.

The researchers would also like to thank the **participants** of this study. Their willingness to dedicate their time and effort to completing the questionnaire has dramatically contributed to the overall success of this research.

We would also like to express our gratitude to our **families** for their unwavering love, encouragement, and patience. Their understanding and belief in our abilities have been a constant source of strength and motivation.

Above all, we would like to express our sincere gratitude to **God** for His guidance and blessings throughout this research project. Without His help, we would not have been able to complete this work successfully. We thank Him for giving us the opportunity to pursue this study and for providing us with the necessary resources and skills. We also thank him for inspiring us with His wisdom and for strengthening us with His grace. We dedicate this paper to Him and to His glory.

While it is impossible to mention everyone, who has contributed to this work, please accept our sincere thanks for your support.

DEDICATION

This research is dedicated to our **beloved parents**, who have been our unwavering source of motivation and strength. They have consistently provided us with moral, spiritual, emotional, and material support, encouraging us even when we contemplated giving up.

We express gratitude to our brothers, sisters, family members, mentors, friends, and classmates who have shared their wisdom and provided motivation throughout our study, enabling us to overcome challenges and complete our research.

Lastly, we dedicate our study to the **Almighty God**, expressing our heartfelt thanks for granting us safety and imparting us with skills, wisdom, and guidance. We acknowledge that all of these blessings come from Him.

ABSTRACT

Title : **ASSESSMENT OF MUSCULOSKELETAL DISORDERS FOR JEEPNEY DRIVERS; A CASE OF SOUTH CEBU**

Researchers : JUVY D. BOLONGAITA
: CHEVILYN ROSE G. GEMPEROSO
: ROGIE Y. MILMAO
: MESSIEH GRACE N. REUMA

Degree : Bachelor of Science in Industrial Engineering

Adviser : ENGR. JIÑA MARIE R. MABANTO

School : Cebu Technological University – Moalboal Campus

Year of Completion : October 2024

No. Pages: 72

This study investigates the prevalence and risk factors of musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) among jeepney drivers operating between Moalboal and Badian. Utilizing the Cornell Musculoskeletal Discomfort Questionnaire (CMDQ) and the Rapid Entire Body Assessment (REBA), the study assesses ergonomic risks associated with prolonged sitting, repetitive movements, and awkward postures commonly experienced by drivers. The findings reveal significant discomfort in the neck (21.15%), lower back (12.83%), and shoulders (7.15%), indicating the impact of prolonged periods behind the wheel. Discomfort in the wrist (6.89%) also emerges as a critical issue. Statistical analysis using Pearson's correlation coefficient shows a weak negative relationship ($r = -0.17$) between working hours and the severity of MSDs, suggesting other contributing factors beyond work duration, such as vehicle ergonomics and health conditions. REBA scores classify all drivers as high-risk (scores of 8-10), underscoring the need for ergonomic interventions, including better seating and work practice improvements, to reduce the risk of MSDs and promote driver well-being.

Keywords: *Musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs), Cornell Musculoskeletal Discomfort Questionnaire (CMDQ), Rapid Entire Body Assessment (REBA)*

TABLE OF CONTENTS

	PAGE
TITLE	I
APPROVAL SHEET	ii
ACKNOWLEDGEMENT	iii
DEDICATION	v
ABSTRACT	vi
TABLE OF CONTENTS	vii
LIST OF FIGURES	ix
LIST OF TABLES	x
ANNEXES	xi
CHAPTER 1	1
THE PROBLEM AND ITS SCOPE	1
Rationale of the Study	1
Theoretical Background	4
Review of Related Literature	10
THE PROBLEM	19
Statement of the Problem	19
Hypotheses	19
Significance of the Study	20
RESEARCH METHODOLOGY	22
Method	22
Flow of the Study	23
Research Environment	25
Research Respondents	25

Research Instruments	26
Data Gathering Procedure	26
Statistical Treatment	27
Definition of Terms	29
CHAPTER 2	31
PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA	31
CHAPTER 3	46
SUMMARY, FINDINGS, CONCLUSION, AND	46
RECOMMENDATION	
SUMMARY OF FINDINGS	46
CONCLUSION	48
RECOMMENDATION	49
BIBLIOGRAPHY	50

LIST OF FIGURES

FIGURE		PAGE
1	Theoretical Framework of the Study	7
2	Research Flow of the Study	23
3	Location of the Study	24
4	Age of the respondents	31
5	Average Working Hours	32
6	Average Trip per day	34
7	Average Interval per trip	35
8	Medical History	36
9	Presence of Discomfort in each Body Part	38
10	Correlation between Working Hours and Risk of MSD	41
11	Rapid Entire Body Assessment	43
12	Jeepney Driver (High Risk)	45

LIST OF TABLES

TABLE		PAGE
1	Discomfort score between body parts using CMDQ	42
2	t-Test: Two Sample Assuming Unequal Variances	44

ANNEXES

ANNEX NO.		PAGE
1	Transmittal Letters	58
2	Survey Questionnaires	62
3	Curriculum Vitae	68

Chapter 1
THE PROBLEM AND ITS SCOPE
INTRODUCTION

Rationale of the Study

Philippines Jeepney is the accessible and cheapest mode of transportation and one of the most popular public transportation in the country. Honored to Filipino's driver for over 70 years can capture their spirit and remind of their cultural significance (Mateo et al., 2020). The jeepney is a utility vehicle, like mini-bus, manufactured by local companies. The application of ergonomic tools, such as posture evaluation devices, has been proposed to optimize driving posture for operators (Bontrup et al., 2019). Studies indicate that discomfort levels are moderately correlated with perceived disability, underscoring the importance of implementing ergonomic interventions and pain management strategies to reduce discomfort.

Drivers have a tendency to overload the vehicle, especially during rush hours. Within the jeepney, the driver's workspace was not physically and mentally comforting because the driver had various positions in order to ease discomfort from static positions. Jeepney drivers' risk of sitting for long periods of time can worsen because of the requirements of their occupation, which could lead to musculoskeletal impairments and other seated activities that are very uncomfortable (Serrano et al., 2019).

Prolonged sitting, especially in the context of jeepney drivers, can have several negative effects on health. Musculoskeletal disorders are of concern in this population, particularly in truck, bus, and taxi drivers. Risk factors for these occupations include long

hours in a sitting position, years in the profession, vehicle ergonomics, and vibration (Pickard et al., 2022). Long term exposure to whole-body vibrations, jerky and repetitive movements, and prolonged sedentary lifestyles, present as key aggravating factors, which increase with years as occupational drivers often spend long hours sitting behind the wheel, which can result in a range of health problems. Jeepney operators, similar to numerous individuals who engage in prolonged periods of sedentary activity, are susceptible to a range of musculoskeletal ailments (Estember & Espinosa, 2020).

Extended periods of sitting while operating a vehicle can significantly impact drivers' health, particularly within the musculoskeletal framework. One of the most prevalent issues is lower back pain, often exacerbated by poor seating ergonomics and limited opportunities for movement. Drivers also frequently report strain in the neck and shoulders, resulting from prolonged static postures and repetitive motions. These health risks are common among professional drivers, with long hours in a seated position, vehicle ergonomics, and vibrations contributing significantly to musculoskeletal disorders (Pickard et al., 2022). Musculoskeletal problems are most commonly reported in the lumbar spine (70%), cervical spine (54%), shoulders (47%), and thoracic spine (36%). Among co-drivers, cervical spine discomfort shows a higher prevalence (62%) compared to drivers (46%). Conversely, drivers report a higher prevalence of hand and wrist discomfort (32%) than co-drivers (9%), likely due to repetitive tasks such as steering and gear shifting. Research indicates that the prevalence of low back pain among rally participants is significantly higher than that generally reported for workers exposed to whole-body vibration, underscoring the unique risks faced by professional drivers (Mansfield & Marshall, 2001).

In addition to musculoskeletal concerns, prolonged sitting for jeepney drivers may contribute to poor circulation and an increased risk of cardiovascular issues. This research study, aims to enhance the overall health and well-being of jeepney drivers operating from Moalboal to Badian and vice versa by assessing the negative effects of prolonged sitting.

Theoretical Background

This study aimed to find the correlation between average working hours and the severity of musculoskeletal disorder experienced by Jeepney drivers. And also, examined the variations in discomfort levels among different work-related groups.

Max Banfield's Posture Theory proposed that poor posture, characterized by the forward placement of the head and shoulders relative to the spine, induced strain on spinal joints and muscles, resulting in long-term consequences such as neck and backaches, arthritis, and spinal injuries. The theory emphasized that this misalignment places downward pressure on chest and abdominal structures, causing tenderness, soreness, and occasional pains, as well as impacting breathing efficiency by restricting lung movement during inhalation. Over time, poor posture may lead to changes in breathing function, occasional breathlessness, and compression of chest air, affecting blood flow and contributing to tiredness, poor concentration, and weakened blood vessels below the chest. Additionally, poor posture can alter the shape and position of the stomach, impair digestion, and predispose individuals to stomach and abdominal pains (Banfield, 2002).

Age plays a significant role in the development of musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) among drivers. As workers age, they become more vulnerable to physical strain due to prolonged sitting and poor posture, which are common in driving occupations. Older drivers often experience more severe discomfort in areas like the lower back and neck, as the physical demands of the job over time reduce the body's ability to cope with poor posture (Pickard et al., 2022).

Working hours also have a critical impact on musculoskeletal health. Long durations of work have been shown to significantly increase the risk of MSDs. As work

hours extend, the body's ability to maintain good posture decreases, leading to discomfort in the neck, shoulders, and back, as demonstrated in studies on interior design students (Rinawati et al., 2023).

The average trips per day further exacerbate ergonomic risks. A study on city bus drivers revealed that approximately 60% of their workday is spent driving, often in unsupported postures, which strain the lower back and surrounding muscles. Additional factors, such as exposure to vibration and repetitive handling tasks, increase the prevalence of musculoskeletal discomfort, emphasizing the importance of posture variation and ergonomic interventions (Okunribido et al., 2007).

Finally, the intervals between trips are crucial for rest and recovery. Shorter intervals do not provide adequate time for muscles to relax, leading to increased fatigue and discomfort. Drivers who take longer rest periods are less likely to experience strain, as posture variation and muscle relaxation are essential to mitigating the risks of prolonged sitting (Atlas et al., 2006).

Good and bad posture are concepts often defined by common beliefs but are complex in their impact on spinal health. Traditionally, "bad posture" is associated with static, flexed spinal postures (such as slouching) that are believed to cause spinal pain. This view is reinforced by common advice like "sit up straight," emphasizing a neutral spine as the ideal posture. However, scientific evidence does not support a direct link between a specific posture and spinal pain. The study challenges this by highlighting that while a neutral spine is often recommended, focusing solely on maintaining such postures may overlook the importance of postural variation. It suggests that regularly changing posture—rather than holding a static "good" posture—can prevent discomfort and musculoskeletal pain. Thus, the idea of good

posture should not be limited to a rigid, fixed position but should include a dynamic approach, where posture is altered frequently to reduce strain on the spine and promote overall spinal health. This approach provides a more individualized and practical perspective, emphasizing that there is no one-size-fits-all solution to posture correction (Mingels, 2023).

Figure 1. Theoretical Framework of the Study

The Cornell Musculoskeletal Discomfort Questionnaires (CMDQ) is formulated by Dr. Alan Hedge and the ergonomics graduate students at Cornell University. It is a data-gathering instrument, designed both for men and women, that evaluates 12 organs in the body in three stages: (1) the frequency of discomfort; (2) discomfort intensity; and (3) the impact on adjusted operating power. Moreover, the 54-question assessment tool has been applied in various occupational settings, including healthcare providers and machine operators, to evaluate musculoskeletal pain. It has three different positions, sitting, standing, and finger parts, and two kinds of gender designed questionnaire, for each a position (Erdoğan et al., 2008).

Rapid Entire Body Assessment (REBA) was developed by Hignett and McAtamney to assess the entire body posture for the risk of Work-Related Musculoskeletal Disorders (WRMSDs). It serves as a practitioner's field tool, specifically designed to be sensitive to unpredictable working postures, particularly in healthcare and service industries. The tool is intended for survey investigations in workplaces where individuals report Work-Related Musculoskeletal Disorders. The method involves assessing critical tasks of a job, scoring posture factors for different body regions (Group A and Group B), considering factors like Load/Force and Coupling, and finally, scoring the overall activity. Scores obtained are then used to determine the level of risk based on tables provided, aiding in the identification and mitigation of ergonomic risks associated with specific work tasks (Hita-Gutiérrez et al., 2020).

The researchers investigated the relationship between the average working hours of jeepney drivers and musculoskeletal disorders based on CMDQ responses. The researchers aimed to understand the severity of MSD experienced by jeepney drivers in relation to the duration of their driving. In addition, the researchers studied

the ergonomic risks associated with their driving tasks using the REBA. This analysis also considered other factors such as average trip per day and average interval per trip.

Review of Related Literature

Musculoskeletal Disorder on Professional Workers/Drivers

Office Workers

In the study entitled "Ergonomic Interventions for Preventing Work-Related Musculoskeletal Disorders of the Upper Limb and Neck Among Office Workers," researchers investigated the prevalence and impact of work-related upper limb and neck musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) in office workers. These MSDs, recognized as common occupational disorders, affecting a significant percentage of office workers, ranging from 20 to 60 percent. The study emphasized the considerable direct and indirect costs associated with work-related upper limb MSDs in regions such as Europe, Australia, and the United States. However, despite indications that ergonomic interventions have potential in mitigating the risk of these disorders, the existing evidence remains unclear (Hoe et al., 2018).

In a study focusing on work-related musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) among office workers at Kerman University of Medical Sciences, the objective was to identify the prevalence of MSDs and associated ergonomic risks (Mohammadipour et al., 2018). The study included all office workers in the university, with a sample size of 129 women and 121 men. Data on MSDs were collected using the Nordic Musculoskeletal Questionnaire, while ergonomic data were obtained through two direct observations using the rapid upper limb assessment (RULA) and the rapid office strain assessment (ROSA) method.

The findings revealed the highest prevalence rates of MSDs in the lower back (72.4%) and neck (55.2%). Postural assessments indicated that 68.8% of participants

required further investigation for posture modification, and 27.6% needed immediate posture adjustments. Workstation analysis showed that a majority of office workers were at a medium (55.2%) and high-risk level (27.6%). Additionally, significant associations were identified between some MSDs in the lower back and neck with the RULA and ROSA scores.

Based on these results, preventive measures for MSDs are recommended. This includes conducting ergonomics workshops to raise awareness among workers about ergonomic factors in the office. Furthermore, incorporating ergonomics training in offices and improving the design of workstations are emphasized as essential strategies for MSD prevention in office settings (Mohammadipour et al., 2018).

Taxi Drivers

The investigation in the Accra Metropolis of Ghana aimed to study the prevalence, body distribution, and determinants of MSDs among urban taxi drivers. The results of the study highlighted a high estimated prevalence of MSDs (70.5%), affecting various body domains such as the lower back, upper back, neck, shoulders, knees, hips/thighs, elbows, ankles/feet, and wrists/hands. Multiple logistic regression analysis revealed that employee drivers, those driving over 12 hours per day or at least 5 days per week, perceiving their job as stressful, and expressing job dissatisfaction faced an elevated risk of developing MSDs. The study underscored the importance of preventive strategies and safety guidelines for mitigating MSDs among urban taxi drivers in Ghana (Abledu et al., 2014).

Furthermore, a study focusing on taxi drivers in the Lucknow district of Uttar Pradesh studied the prevalence of work-related MSDs in various body segments. Involving 120 drivers with a daily driving experience exceeding 8 hours, the study

utilized a self-made checklist to assess MSDs in areas like the head and neck, upper extremities, thoracic extremities, and lower extremities. Statistical analysis using SPSS 20.0 revealed a highly significant difference in the prevalence of work-related MSDs across different body segments. The findings suggested that (Seva et al., 2011) the profession of taxi driving, marked by prolonged driving durations and poor workplace design, increased the risk of musculoskeletal disorders (Srivastava & Kiran, 2014).

Bus Drivers

In "Work-related musculoskeletal disorders in urban bus drivers of Hong Kong", the study involved 481 bus drivers, including 404 males and 77 females, operating double-deck buses, a major mode of public transportation in the densely populated city of Hong Kong. The findings highlighted a high prevalence of WMSD among the drivers, affecting various body segments. The areas with the highest 12-month prevalence rates of musculoskeletal discomfort included the neck, back, shoulder, and knee/thigh, ranging from 35% to 60%. The study identified occupational factors like prolonged sitting and anthropometric mismatch as significant contributors to musculoskeletal discomfort. Despite male drivers generally having more years of work experience, both male and female drivers shared similar daily workloads (Szeto & Lam, 2007).

Similar to a study "Prevalence of work-related musculoskeletal disorders among occupational bus drivers of Karnataka, South India", 301 full-time bus drivers from the central division of KSRTC in Bengaluru were examined. Approximately 55.8% of the drivers had experienced WMSD, with the highest prevalence observed in the age group of 29–39 years (53.5%), followed by the age group of >40 years. The study

emphasized specific work-related and lifestyle/health-related factors associated with WMSD in bus drivers of Karnataka (Pradeepkumar et al., 2020).

Jeepney Drivers

In a study conducted on Filipino jeepney drivers inside the UP Diliman campus, researchers aimed to assess the ergonomic conditions of the drivers' workspaces in relation to their anthropometric measurements and vehicle dimensions. Jeepney drivers in the Philippines typically work long hours in constrained spaces that demand sustained awkward postures, often leading to physical strain and discomfort. This study was motivated by the need to identify specific vehicle-related factors contributing to awkward postures and discomfort among drivers, which could increase their risk for developing musculoskeletal disorders (Coz et al., 2015).

The research included a comprehensive survey of jeepney drivers to gather data on the discomfort experienced while driving. Additionally, the study involved direct measurements of the drivers' workspace, including seating positions, distance from the steering wheel, and visibility factors, to compare with the drivers' anthropometric dimensions. Results revealed several ergonomic challenges, such as insufficient space between the driver's seat and the steering wheel, which restricted driver mobility. The study also highlighted the limited height of the windshield, which obstructed the driver's line of sight and required frequent forward-leaning postures to view traffic signs. These conditions, compounded by repetitive movements like gear shifting and prolonged sitting, contributed to increased musculoskeletal strain on the drivers (Coz et al., 2015).

Similar to a study investigating the ergonomic challenges faced by jeepney drivers in the Philippines, researchers evaluated the dimensions of the drivers'

workspace and their alignment with anthropometric data collected from 100 drivers. Jeepneys, commonly known as a popular and cost-effective form of transportation, expose drivers to prolonged awkward postures and unnecessary physical tasks, which can lead to musculoskeletal strain and discomfort. This study aimed to identify specific ergonomic hazards in the jeepney driver's workspace and develop an analytical model using Computer Aided Three-dimensional Interactive Application (CATIA) software to redesign the space with improved ergonomics and reduced physical strain (Seva et al., 2011).

To assess the drivers' postures, the study utilized the Rapid Upper Limb Assessment (RULA) method, which helped pinpoint areas where postural improvements were needed. The assessment yielded high RULA scores of 3 and 4 for common postures, such as hands on the steering wheel and shifting gears, indicating a need for ergonomic improvements. Additionally, the task analysis revealed that certain actions, like reaching back to hand change to passengers, contributed to unnecessary movement and discomfort. The redesign included adjustments to workspace dimensions that aligned better with the reach, height, and strength requirements of drivers in the 95th percentile. The proposed modifications featured improved placement of vehicle controls, redesigned money holders, and new fare collection options to reduce awkward postures and unnecessary tasks (Seva et al., 2011).

The re-designed workspace resulted in more favorable RULA scores in a simulation model, suggesting decreased postural strain for drivers. Driver responses to the proposed fare collection system were also positive, indicating practical benefits of the ergonomic changes. The study's findings underline the importance of ergonomic

considerations in vehicle design to minimize health risks and enhance driver comfort. The authors recommended further research, including full-scale prototyping, to assess the practical viability of the redesigned workspace. Moreover, they emphasized the need for jeepney manufacturers to address additional issues such as vibration and force exertion on controls, including the steering wheel and pedals, which can further impact driver discomfort (Seva et al., 2011).

Previous study on Musculoskeletal Assessment Tools

Nordic Musculoskeletal Questionnaire (NMQ)

Nordic Musculoskeletal Questionnaire (NMQ) has played a major role in evaluating musculoskeletal complaints. Developed from a project funded by the Nordic Council of Ministers, the NMQ aimed to create a standardized methodology for comparing low back, neck, shoulder, and general complaints in epidemiological studies, without being intended for clinical diagnosis (Crawford, 2007).

A study conducted in Qom, Iran, focused on assessing musculoskeletal disorders among lorry drivers. This cross-sectional study involved drivers with at least 5 years of job experience. The research utilized the Iranian version of the standardized Nordic Questionnaire (NMQ) to analyze musculoskeletal symptoms. The questionnaire covered a range of body areas and provided insights into the prevalence and severity of pain or discomfort experienced by the drivers during specified time frames (Mozafari et al., 2014).

The NMQ, originally proposed by Kourinka in 1987, has been a widely adopted tool in various studies assessing musculoskeletal problems in different occupational settings, including computer and call center workers, car drivers, and forestry workers (Mozafari et al., 2014).

Rapid Upper Limb Assessment (RULA)

The Rapid Upper Limb Assessment (RULA), introduced by McAtamney and Corlett (1993), has emerged as a valuable survey method in ergonomics investigations, particularly in workplaces where work-related upper limb disorders are prevalent. This tool facilitates an evaluation of postures concerning the neck, trunk, and upper limbs, encompassing considerations of muscle function and external loads on the body. Particularly, RULA doesn't need specialized equipment, making it a practical choice for rapid assessments in various work environments (McAtamney & Corlett, 1993; Hignett & McAtamney, 2000).

In a study conducted by Chand and Bhasi, the application of RULA in assessing the anthropometric characteristics and postures of male public transportation bus drivers in India, was studied. The research specifically addressed the comfort of bus drivers, emphasizing the correlation between RULA posture scores for various body regions and self-reported discomforts in corresponding areas. The study revealed substantial scores for neck and trunk posture, indicating significant loading in these regions. Importantly, the study recommended immediate posture modifications for participating drivers and underscored the significance of designing ergonomic bus driver cabins (Chand & Bhasi, 2023).

Cornell Musculoskeletal System Discomfort Questionnaire (CMDQ)

The Cornell Musculoskeletal Discomfort Questionnaires (CMDQ), developed by Dr. Alan Hedge and Cornell University's ergonomics graduate students, are instrumental tools for assessing musculoskeletal discomfort.

In a study entitled "Working Posture Evaluation of Bus Drivers—Using CMDQ and RULA Technique," conducted by Soumyajit Das and colleagues, the focus was

on addressing work-related musculoskeletal disorders (WMSDs) prevalent among bus drivers, with an emphasis on ergonomic interventions. The study encompassed psycho-physiological aspects of bus driving, evaluating driving posture and seats as key factors influencing musculoskeletal symptoms.

To collect musculoskeletal health data, CMDQ was used, providing insights into the prevalence of discomfort in various body segments. Subsequently, the researchers utilized the Rapid Upper Limb Assessment (RULA) technique to analyze video-captured driving postures. Results revealed a correlation between CMDQ outcomes and RULA, emphasizing the vulnerability of body segments like the lower back, neck, upper arm, lower legs, and wrists to musculoskeletal disorders due to prolonged bus driving (Ogedengbe et al., 2022).

Rapid Entire Body Assessment (REBA)

Rapid Entire Body Assessment (REBA) is a postural analysis tool developed to address the dynamic and unpredictable working postures found in healthcare and service industries. The tool incorporates both static and dynamic postural loading factors, human-load interface (coupling), and introduces a novel concept of a gravity-assisted upper limb position (Hignett & McAtamney, 2000).

In a study titled "Analysis of work posture using Rapid Entire Body Assessment (REBA) as the risk factor of work-related musculoskeletal disorders among bus drivers in Bandar Lampung City," the focus was on identifying work-related musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) among bus drivers and their association with work posture. The study, a cross-sectional analysis involving inter-provincial bus drivers, utilized the Nordic Body Map to assess MSDs distribution and REBA to evaluate the level of MSD risk based on work posture.

The research underscores the critical role of REBA in assessing work-related musculoskeletal risks and the importance of ergonomic interventions to enhance the well-being of bus drivers. The integration of REBA as a practical field tool contributes to understanding and addressing unpredictable working postures, promoting a safer and healthier work environment for bus drivers (Mayasari & Octaviani, 2017).

This research focused on identifying the risk and prevalence of musculoskeletal disorders (MSD) among Jeepney drivers, assessing factors such as prolonged period of sitting, uncomfortable posture, and repetitive movements. This study adopted a unique approach by investigating: (1) the severity of MSD experienced by jeepney drivers in relation to the duration of their driving; (2) identify and evaluate ergonomic risks specific to their driving tasks, emphasizing body positioning and movements.

The results in this study should justify the key factors contributing to musculoskeletal disorders among jeepney drivers. The study's approach involves surveys using Cornell Musculoskeletal Discomfort Questionnaires (CMDQ) and Rapid Entire Body Assessment (REBA) to collect information on the challenges faced by jeepney drivers. This structured method ensures a comprehensive examination of ergonomic risks and demographic factors, contributing to a thorough analysis of the situation.

THE PROBLEM

Statement of the Problem

This research aimed to investigate the occupational challenges faced by Jeepney drivers operating from Moalboal to Badian and vice versa.

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the demographics of the jeepney drivers?
 - 1.1. Age;
 - 1.2. Average working hours;
 - 1.3. Average trip per day;
 - 1.4. Average interval per trip;
2. What Musculoskeletal Disorders are present in Jeepney drivers?
3. Is there a significant relationship between working time of the jeepney drivers and MSD?
4. What is the hazard level of the Jeepney drivers using REBA?
5. Based on the findings, what recommendations can be formulated?

Hypothesis

To test the significant aspect of the study, the following hypothesis were formulated:

Is there a significant relationship between the working hours of jeepney drivers and the occurrence of musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs)?

Null Hypothesis (H_0): There is no significant relationship between the working hours of jeepney drivers and the occurrence of musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs).

Alternative Hypothesis (H_1): There is a significant relationship between the working hours of jeepney drivers and the occurrence of musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs).

Significance of the study

This study will benefit the following:

Jeepney Driver. This study aims to improve the well-being of Jeepney drivers by identifying and addressing ergonomic issues that affect their physical health and job performance. By reducing chronic pain and improving working conditions, this study hopes to increase job satisfaction and productivity among drivers, ultimately contributing to a better quality of life.

Family of Jeepney Drivers. By addressing the ergonomic issues faced by drivers, this study indirectly benefits their families by improving the physical health and financial stability of drivers. Healthier drivers are more likely to maintain steady employment, which positively impacts the economic and emotional well-being of their families.

Future Researchers. This study can serve as a reference for future research related to occupational health in public transportation. The insights gained from this research could encourage further investigations into the health and safety of other public transportation workers, fostering the development of more effective ergonomic strategies in the industry.

Community. The study's findings can promote awareness and discussion about the health and safety of jeepney drivers within the community. Improved working conditions for drivers can lead to a healthier population and contribute to the overall well-being of the community.

Jeepney Manufacturers. Manufacturers can benefit from this study by gaining insights into the ergonomic needs of drivers, allowing them to design vehicles that better accommodate driver comfort and safety. This can lead to enhanced vehicle designs that prioritize the health and productivity of drivers.

Businesses Providing Customization Services. Businesses that specialize in customizing vehicles can utilize the findings of this study to offer ergonomic solutions specifically designed to meet the needs of jeepney drivers. This can create a market for innovative adaptations that enhance driver comfort and reduce the risk of musculoskeletal disorders.

METHODOLOGY

This section of the study introduces the research methodology. It includes the study's design, study's flow, study's location, the respondents, the data collection procedure, the instrument used, the treatment of data, and the study's validity and reliability.

Method

This study used a quantitative approach, with two different survey questionnaires distributed. The first was a standard survey questionnaire designed by the researcher to collect demographic information and other relevant data. The second was the Cornell Musculoskeletal Disorders Questionnaire (CMDQ), which focuses on identifying which regions of the human body experience the most musculoskeletal pain. Next, the researchers captured video of the drivers while they were driving to assess their posture, which was then rated using the Rapid Entire Body Assessment (REBA). The purpose of the first questionnaire was to collect demographic data such as age, average working hours, average trips per day, and average interval per trip among drivers. The second questionnaire aimed to identify the body parts most impacted by musculoskeletal disorders. REBA was used to assess the ergonomic risks associated with their driving tasks, focusing on evaluating the posture and movements of the drivers to determine potential risks for musculoskeletal disorders. The data collected from these studies will be analyzed and interpreted using Simple Percentage and Pearson's Correlation Coefficient.

Figure 2. Flow of the Study

Figure 3. Location of the Study

Research Environment

The study was conducted in District VII of Cebu Province, focusing specifically on the municipalities of Moalboal and Badian. These municipalities are located in the southern part of Cebu Island, along the western seaboard, an area renowned for its vibrant tourism industry and agricultural roots. The jeepney drivers' route begins at the Badian Public Market, where passengers are picked up before heading to Gaisano Grand, and then returning to the Badian Public Market, where drivers line up and await their next trip.

The demographic composition of the region is a mix of local residents and tourists. Moalboal is famous for its pristine beaches and diving spots, contributing significantly to its tourism-driven economy. Badian, in contrast, relies more on its agricultural activities, particularly farming and fishing, which form the backbone of its local economy.

Respondents

The respondents in this study were selected based on specific criteria to ensure their relevance to the research objectives. First, the participants had to be jeepney drivers, as the study focuses on musculoskeletal health risks related to driving. They were required to be operating in the municipalities of Moalboal and Badian, as the study is specifically aimed at assessing the working conditions of drivers in these areas. Respondents were asked to voluntarily agree to participate in the study after being fully informed of its purpose, procedures, and potential risks, ensuring ethical compliance and respect for their autonomy.

Sampling Method

The study used a convenience sampling technique in selecting the respondents to participate in the survey questionnaire. Respondents were chosen based on convenience in terms of availability, reach, and accessibility.

Instrument

This study used a structured survey approach through questionnaires designed to gather relevant information concerning the difficulties faced by Jeepney drivers. The selected respondents were surveyed through a questionnaire designed by the researchers, second is Cornell Musculoskeletal Discomfort Questionnaires (CMDQ), and lastly the respondents were assessed using Rapid Entire Body Assessment (REBA). The main purpose of the standard questionnaire was to collect relevant data such as age, average working hours, average trip per day, and average interval per trip. The purpose of CMDQ was to identify the specific regions of the body that is experiencing musculoskeletal pain, and for REBA was to identify and evaluate ergonomic risks specific to their driving tasks, emphasizing body positioning and movements.

Data Gatherings Procedure

The researchers used two survey questionnaires to gather data from the respondents. An approval forms was obtained from both the campus director and the town mayor. Additionally, a consent form was distributed to and approved by the Jeepney drivers before the study was conducted. The first questionnaire covered the demographics of the respondents, while the second questionnaire used was the Cornell Musculoskeletal Disorder Questionnaire (CMDQ). Lastly, the respondents were assessed using the Rapid Entire Body Assessment (REBA). The data gathered

from these tools helped pinpoint the regions of the body where the drivers experienced the most discomfort or strain. Similarly, the REBA identified specific body areas prone to ergonomic risks during their driving tasks. The responses were converted into numerical data for statistical analysis.

Statistical Treatment

Descriptive statistics, including simple percentage, will profile respondents based on age, average working hours, average trips per day, and average interval per trip. Pearson's correlation coefficient will assess relationships between working hours and musculoskeletal disorder severity. This approach allows for a comprehensive examination of the interactive effects of multiple factors on the dependent variable.

The formula for Pearson's correlation is:

$$r = \frac{\sum (x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum (x_i - \bar{x})^2 \sum (y_i - \bar{y})^2}}$$

Where:

r = correlation coefficient

$x_{\{i\}}$ = values of the x-variable in a sample

\bar{x} = mean of the values of the x-variable

$y_{\{i\}}$ = values of the y-variable in a sample

\bar{y} = mean of the values of the y-variable

This method will measure if there is positive (+1) correlation between the variables which means that the working time, the more he is experiencing musculoskeletal pain. If the measurement will determine a negative relationship (-1)

this means that as one variable increases, the other decreases. If the analysis will determine a zero (0) relation, then there is no relationship among the variables.

The Rapid Entire Body Assessment (REBA) is a systematic ergonomic assessment tool used to evaluate musculoskeletal disorder (MSD) risks in job tasks. It analyzes posture, force exertion, and biomechanical loading, assigning scores to body segments and forces. The tool classifies overall risk levels and provides recommendations for risk reduction. REBA is applied in various industries for workplace ergonomics, aiding in preventive measures and continuous improvement. The selection of the postures to be evaluated should be based on a worker interview and initial observation. Limitations include subjectivity and the potential oversimplification of complex tasks. Proper training and combining it with other assessments enhance effectiveness (Hignett, 1998; McAtamney & Hignett, 1995).

Score	Level of MSD Risk
1	negligible risk, no action required
2-3	low risk, change may be needed
4-7	medium risk, further investigation, change soon
8-10	high risk, investigate and implement change
11+	very high risk, implement change

Definition of Terms

To better understand the terminologies used in this study, the following terms are defined and clarified in the context of this research:

Assessment - Used to evaluate ergonomic risks and musculoskeletal conditions of jeepney drivers through tools like CMDQ and REBA.

Discomfort - Refers to the physical unease reported by drivers, measured in specific body parts using the CMDQ.

Ergonomic Risk - Assessed using REBA, focusing on hazards in driving postures and repetitive tasks.

Ergonomics - The study's foundation, addressing workplace improvements for drivers.

Hazard Level - Defined by REBA scores, indicating the risk of MSDs due to driving tasks.

Jeepney - The primary vehicle studied, highlighting its design's impact on driver ergonomics.

Jeepney Drivers - The study's respondents, whose work environment and habits were analyzed for ergonomic risks.

Musculoskeletal Disorder (MSD) - Conditions identified in drivers, such as back and wrist pain, linked to job demands.

Posture - Assessed via video analysis and REBA to determine risk factors.

Prolonged - Used to describe the extended sitting times of drivers during their daily work.

Repetitive Movement - Actions like gear-shifting and steering evaluated for their contribution to MSDs.

Working Time of Jeepney Drivers - The total hours drivers spent on their routes, analyzed for correlations with MSD prevalence.

CHAPTER 2

PRESENTATION, DATA ANALYSIS, AND INTERPRETATION

In this chapter, the researcher presents and discusses the results of the data collected through survey and questionnaire of the Jeepney drivers operating between Moalboal and Badian. The results of this study are illustrated using tables and graph. The arrangement of the data is presented in a way that corresponds to the specific problems outlined in chapter 1.

PRESENTATION OF RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The subsequent graphs present and discuss the profile of the respondents and other research findings. There was a total of 10 respondents in this research. They are the Jeepney drivers operating between Moalboal and Badian.

2.1. Age

Figure 4. Age of the Respondents

This data presents the age of the respondents. It indicates a predominance of older jeepney drivers, with ages 51-60 years old (40%) and 41-50 years old (30%) comprising a total of 70% of the sample. This suggests that the majority of drivers are

approaching or are already in their later middle age, which is significant due to the increased physical strain and ergonomic risks associated with aging. According to (Cantin et al., 2009), older drivers may experience higher mental workloads and longer reaction times, particularly in complex driving situations, which can worsen the physical demands of their role. The small percentage of younger drivers, with only 10% aged 21-30 years old and 31-40 years old, highlights a potential gap in the influx of new drivers, possibly pointing to recruitment challenges or a shift in job attractiveness. The presence of drivers aging 61-70 years old (10%) further emphasizes the longevity of some individuals in the profession, which may be driven by economic necessity or insufficient retirement options.

2.2. Average Working Hours

Figure 5. Average Working Hours

The data shows that 60% of the respondents work 10 hours per day, 30% work 12 hours per day, and 10% work 8 hours per day. The majority of jeepney drivers (60%) are working 10-hour shifts, which is the most common work duration reported.

This extended working period can lead to increased fatigue and strain, potentially increasing ergonomic and health issues.

Shift work and long work hours increase the risk for reduced performance on the job, obesity, injuries, and a wide range of chronic diseases (Caruso, 2014). This is particularly relevant for jeepney drivers, where prolonged shifts may amplify the risk of musculoskeletal disorders and general health problems. A significant proportion (30%) of drivers work even longer, with 12-hour shifts, which may further worsen these challenges. Only 10% of drivers work 8-hour shifts, which are typically more manageable but less common.

The reason for longer working hours may be driven by several factors. Economic necessity is a primary reason, as many drivers may need to work extended hours to earn sufficient income to support their families. Additionally, the nature of the job, which can be highly competitive and irregular in terms of passenger demand, may force drivers to work longer hours to maximize their earnings. Limited job security and the absence of formalized benefits or retirement plans may also force drivers to work extended shifts to ensure financial stability

2.3. Average trip per day

Figure 6. Average Trip per Day

This data indicates the average number of trips a driver can complete per day. The majority of jeepney drivers (60%) complete 3 rounds of trips daily, whereas 40% complete 4 rounds, despite all driving the same route. This variation in trip frequency can be influenced by several factors. Drivers who manage 4 rounds per day may face higher passenger demand or choose to work longer hours to increase their earnings. They might be motivated by the need for additional income or to make the most of peak travel times, leading to a higher number of trips. Time poverty, a condition where individuals work long hours without choice due to financial constraints, as drivers may feel forced to work extra hours to avoid financial difficulty (Bardasi & Wodon, 2010).

Conversely, drivers completing 3 rounds may experience lower demand or prefer a more balanced workday to avoid excessive fatigue. The nature of the route itself, such as its length and traffic conditions, may impact how many trips a driver can

comfortably complete in a day. Variations in driving speed, waiting times, and vehicle condition can also contribute to the difference in the number of trips.

2.4. Average interval per trip

Figure 7. Average interval per trip

Figure 7 shows that 50 percent of the respondents have an interval of 2 hours between trips, while the other 50 percent have an interval of 3 hours between trips. Drivers with a 2-hour interval between trips may be operating in a context where passenger turnover is quicker, possibly due to fewer drivers on the route, which reduces waiting times. Shorter intervals could indicate more frequent but shorter breaks or faster turnaround times, leading to higher daily earnings. However, these shorter intervals might also result in increased stress and less time for rest between trips, which can affect driver fatigue and overall well-being.

Regular rest breaks can be an effective means of maintaining performance and managing fatigue. Research indicates that while two-hourly breaks are common in many settings, shorter intervals may not provide adequate recovery time, potentially

increasing fatigue-related risks (Tucker, 2003) Conversely, drivers with a 3-hour interval might experience longer waits between trips, which could be due to less frequent passenger demand or longer loading times because there are more drivers on the route. While this longer downtime allows for more rest, it may also lead to reduced earnings if fewer passengers are served.

Figure 8. Medical History

This data shows the medical history of the respondents. From the surveyed drivers, 10 percent have a history of kidney issues and arthritis, while 20 percent have high blood pressure. The majority, 70 percent, reported having no known medical conditions. Kidney problems can be serious, affecting overall health and energy levels. Drivers with such conditions may experience fatigue, which can impact their ability to drive safely and effectively. Similarly, arthritis can cause joint pain and stiffness, which may be worsened by the physical demands of driving, such as prolonged sitting and handling the vehicle. This condition can lead to discomfort and reduced mobility, making it challenging for drivers to perform their duties effectively. High blood pressure

is a significant health concern, increasing the risk of cardiovascular diseases and stroke.

Jeepney drivers often face extended working hours and prolonged sitting, along with exposure to various stressors such as traffic congestion and passenger interactions. These factors can contribute to the development and worsening of medical conditions. Limited access to regular healthcare, financial constraints, and the physically demanding nature of their work can also aggravate existing health issues. Additionally, the combination of stress, lack of movement, and unhealthy lifestyle practices, such as irregular meals or poor diet, may further increase medical conditions among jeepney drivers.

Furthermore, a study indicates that chronic medical conditions can significantly affect driving performance. A systematic review found that drivers with chronic pain engage in risk-compensatory strategies but also face increased crash risks and altered driving behaviors (Vaezipour et al., 2022). This suggests that conditions like arthritis and high blood pressure, which may lead to chronic pain, could similarly impair the driving abilities of jeepney drivers and elevate the likelihood of accidents.

2. Prevalence of MSD among Jeepney Drivers

Figure 9. Presence of Discomfort in each Body Part

The table presents the distribution of discomfort experienced by the jeepney drivers in various body parts. The highest percentage of discomfort was reported in the neck and wrists, with 90% of respondents reporting pain in these areas. This high prevalence of neck discomfort is likely due to prolonged periods of sitting in a fixed position while driving, exacerbated by the need for frequent head movements to check mirrors and traffic conditions, which adds strain to the neck muscles (Dhaiban et al., 2023) Similarly, 90% of respondents experience discomfort in both the right and left wrists, attributed to the repetitive motions required to operate the steering wheel, shift gears, and maneuver the vehicle, placing considerable strain on the wrists (MUGGLETON et al., 1999)

Discomfort in both shoulders (80%) suggests that drivers often adopt awkward postures or perform repetitive tasks that involve overreaching movements, linked to handling the steering wheel, interacting with passengers, and making frequent stops.

Additionally, the lower back is another area of concern, with 70% of respondents reporting pain. This discomfort is likely caused by prolonged sitting in inadequately supported seating. Jeepney drivers often spend hours in fixed positions without sufficient lumbar support, leading to compression of the spine and muscle strain in the lower back. A cross-sectional study by Tamrin et al. (2007), commercial vehicle drivers found a high prevalence of low back pain (60.4%), highlighting the significant impact of factors such as awkward posture, and prolonged sitting on lower back discomfort.

Other areas affected include the hips and buttocks, with 60% of respondents reporting discomfort, while 50% report knee discomfort. The thighs and lower legs had the lowest reported discomfort, with only 30%. These areas are subjected to prolonged immobility while seated, which may cause the joints to become stiff and painful due to the constrained driving posture. Additionally, factors such as the frequent use of the brake and clutch pedals could further contribute to knee pain (Muggleton et al., 1999) highlight how repetitive manual activities and poorly designed work environments can exacerbate such discomfort, increasing the risk of musculoskeletal disorders.

Table 1. Discomfort Score between body parts using CMDQ

Body Part	Frequency	Discomfort	Interference	Discomfort Score	%
Neck	21.5	13	12	3354	21.15
Right Shoulder	14	9	9	1134	7.15
Left Shoulder	14	9	9	1134	7.15
Upper Back	12.5	8	7	700	4.41
Right Upper Arm	11.5	7	7	563.5	3.55
Left Upper Arm	11.5	7	7	563.5	3.55
Lower Back	18.5	10	11	2035	12.83
Right Forearm	14	9	9	1134	7.15
Left Forearm	14	9	9	1134	7.15
Right Wrist	13.5	9	9	1093.5	6.89
Left Wrist	13.5	9	9	1093.5	6.89
Hip/ Buttocks	13	8	8	832	5.24
Right Thigh	6.5	4	4	104	0.65
Left Thigh	6.5	4	4	104	0.65
Right Knee	9.5	7	6	399	2.51
Left Knee	9.5	7	6	399	2.51
Right Lower Leg	4.5	3	3	40.5	0.25
Left Lower Leg	4.5	3	3	40.5	0.25

The table above shows that the neck ranks as the most affected area with the highest discomfort score of 3354, representing 21.15% of the total discomfort. This is followed by the lower back, with a discomfort score of 2035, accounting for 12.83%. Both shoulders report discomfort scores of 1134, representing 7.15% of the overall discomfort. The wrists account for 6.89% of the discomfort with a score of 1093.5. The hips/buttocks show considerable discomfort with a score of 832, accounting for 5.24%. The upper back has a discomfort score of 700 (4.41%).

Other notable areas include the right upper arm and left upper arm, each with a discomfort score of 563.5 (3.55%), while both forearms (right and left) report discomfort scores of 1134 (7.15%). Additionally, both knees report discomfort scores of 399 (2.51%). Lastly, both thighs show lower discomfort scores of 104 (0.65%), and

both lower legs report scores of 40.5 (0.25%), indicating a lower prevalence of discomfort in these regions compared to the other body parts assessed.

3. Correlation Between MSD Risk and Working Hours

Figure 10. Correlation Between MSD Risk and Working Hours

The graph shows the correlation between working hours and the risk of musculoskeletal disorders (MSD) among jeepney drivers. The Pearson's correlation coefficient $r = -0.17$ indicates a weak negative correlation between working time and Musculoskeletal Disorders (MSD). This means that as working time increases, there is a slight tendency for MSD to increase, but the relationship is not strong. The coefficient of determination $R^2 = 0.0289$ further reveals that only 2.89% of the variance in MSD can be explained by working time. This low value suggests that working time is not a significant predictor of MSD, implying that other factors, such as ergonomic conditions, work environment, or individual health factors, likely have a more substantial influence on the development of MSD. A previous research by Serrano-Fernández et al. (2019), indicated that multiple factors beyond working time, such as posture, vibrations, and stress, contribute to the development of musculoskeletal

disorders in professional drivers. In summary, while there is a weak negative relationship between working time and MSD, the impact of working time on MSD is minimal, and other variables should be considered to fully understand the factors contributing to MSD (Serrano-Fernández et al., 2019).

Table 2. t-Test: Two Sample Assuming Unequal Variances

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances		
	<i>Working Hours</i>	<i>Risk of MSD</i>
Mean	10.4	1.1
Variance	1.6	0.02
Observations (n)	10	10
Standard Error (SE)	0.4	0.14
Hypothesized Mean		
Difference		
df	10	
t Stat	1.79	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.053	
t Critical one-tail	1.81	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.107	
t Critical two-tail	2.22	

The t-test results in the table compare the means of working hours and the risk of musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) among jeepney drivers, assuming unequal variances between the two variables. The average working hours for the drivers is 10.4 hours per day, while the average risk of MSD score is 1.1. The variance in working hours is relatively low, at 1.6, indicating that most drivers work around 10 hours daily. However, the variance for the risk of MSD score is lower, at 0.02, suggesting a small variation in MSD risk scores among the drivers.

The calculated t-statistic for this comparison is 1.79, with a degree of freedom (df) of 10. The one-tailed p-value is 0.053, and the two-tailed p-value is 0.107. Both p-

values are greater than the conventional significance level of 0.05. Since the p-values exceed 0.05, this result indicates that the difference between the means of working hours and MSD risk is not statistically significant. Additionally, the calculated t-statistic of 1.79 is slightly less than the critical values for both one-tailed (1.81) and two-tailed (2.22) tests. Therefore, we fail to reject the null hypothesis, suggesting that there is no statistically significant relationship between working hours and MSD risk among jeepney drivers.

This finding implies that, within this sample, the duration of working hours may not have a direct impact on the risk of musculoskeletal disorders. Other factors could be influencing MSD risk among jeepney drivers beyond the hours they spend working each day.

4. Rapid Entire Body Assessment

Figure 11. Rapid Entire Body Assessment

The findings from the Rapid Entire Body Assessment (REBA) indicate that all surveyed jeepney drivers operating between Moalboal and Badian fall within the high-risk category (scores of 8-10) for musculoskeletal issues.

These REBA scores reflect the physical demands placed on the drivers while operating their vehicles. High scores suggest that drivers frequently maintain awkward postures, such as poor seating positions, which lead to strain in the lower back and neck. Additionally, they engage in repetitive motions like shifting gears and adjusting their position to check mirrors, while applying significant force when pressing pedals. These factors collectively contribute to an increased risk of musculoskeletal disorders.

The high-risk categorization underscores the urgent need for targeted interventions to prevent discomfort and potential injuries among these drivers. Repetitive manual tasks and awkward postures are well-known contributors to upper limb disorders across various industries. A study by Mokarami et al. (2017) examined harmful postures among tractor drivers in Iran, using the REBA method to analyze body postures linked to musculoskeletal disorders. Their findings highlight the importance of ergonomic interventions to mitigate risks associated with poor posture in driving occupations, reinforcing the need for similar improvements for jeepney drivers.

Figure 12. Jeepney Driver (High Risk)

CHAPTER 3

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This section illustrates the comprehensive results of the study. It includes the summary of findings, conclusion, and recommendation. The discussion is structured according to the sub-problem outlined in Chapter 1.

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

This study assessed the ergonomic challenges and musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) experienced by Jeepney drivers operating between Moalboal and Badian. It aimed to examine how prolonged sitting, repetitive movements, and poor posture affect the health of drivers, with a specific focus on identifying which body parts are most affected. The study also aimed to study the relationship between working hours and the severity of MSD symptoms, suggesting that longer working hours might lead to increased discomfort.

To collect data, the researchers used video recordings to analyze the drivers' posture and repetitive movements while driving. Two questionnaires were used: a demographic survey and the Cornell Musculoskeletal Discomfort Questionnaire (CMDQ). Ergonomic risks were evaluated using the Rapid Entire Body Assessment (REBA) tool, which assigns risk scores based on posture and movement. Statistical methods such as Pearson's Correlation Coefficient were utilized to analyze the relationship between working hours and MSDs.

The findings show that the respondents, all male, ranged in age from 21 to 70 years, with the majority working 10 to 12 hours per day and completing 3 to 4 trips with intervals of 2 to 3 hours between trips. Health concerns were prevalent, with the most

common discomfort reported in the neck, lower back, and shoulder, attributed to prolonged sitting and repetitive motions. Around 30% of the drivers had pre-existing medical conditions, including high blood pressure, arthritis, and kidney problems.

Pearson's Correlation Coefficient analysis revealed a weak negative correlation ($r = -0.17$) between working hours and MSD, indicating that while there was a slight increase in MSD symptoms with longer working hours, the relationship was not statistically significant. This suggests that working hours alone do not significantly influence MSD symptoms among drivers.

The REBA assessment revealed that all drivers were at high risk for developing MSDs, with scores between 8 and 10. This underscores the critical ergonomic issues in their working environment, particularly due to prolonged sitting, awkward postures, and repetitive motions.

Further analysis of discomfort scores reveals that the neck is the most affected area, with a high discomfort score of 3354 (21.15%), followed by the lower back at 2035 (12.83%), highlighting significant strain. Both shoulders and forearms also show notable discomfort, each with scores of 1134 (7.15%). The wrists, hips/buttocks, and upper back are additional areas of concern, with scores of 1093.5 (6.89%), 832 (5.24%), and 700 (4.41%), respectively, reflecting physical stress from prolonged sitting and movement.

In summary, the study highlights the significant ergonomic challenges faced by Jeepney drivers in the Moalboal and Badian route. The drivers are at high risk for MSDs, particularly in the neck, lower back, shoulders, and forearms, due to prolonged sitting and repetitive movements. Although working hours were not found to

significantly influence the severity of MSDs, the high REBA scores emphasize the need for interventions to reduce the drivers' ergonomic risks and improve their overall health.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that high levels of discomfort were identified among Jeepney drivers, particularly in the neck, lower back, shoulders, and forearms, as assessed using the Cornell Musculoskeletal Discomfort Questionnaire and the Rapid Entire Body Assessment (REBA). The REBA scores classified all respondents as high-risk for developing musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs), primarily due to static postures, cramped seating arrangements, and repetitive arm and leg movements during driving. The lack of proper lumbar support and poor seating adjustments further worsen these risks, contributing to the high REBA scores.

The data shows a weak negative correlation between working hours and MSD symptoms, implying that while longer working hours may be associated with a slight increase in discomfort, this relationship is not strong or statistically significant. This suggests that other factors, such as individual health conditions, may have a more substantial impact on the drivers' musculoskeletal health.

Overall, the combination of CMDQ and REBA results underscores the significant ergonomic risks faced by Jeepney drivers. Poor posture, fixed seating positions, and the absence of proper ergonomic support make drivers prone to chronic pain and MSDs. While working hours alone were not strong predictors of MSDs, other variables, including posture and vehicle ergonomics, play a critical role in the development of these disorders.

RECOMMENDATION

In accordance with the findings and conclusion made in this study, the followings are recommended:

Despite the unexpected results of this study, the researchers recommend incorporating additional factors that could influence the musculoskeletal disorders experienced by jeepney drivers, such as their daily activities outside of driving. It is also suggested that future studies replicate this research with a larger and more diverse group of respondents to enhance the generalizability of the findings.

Based on REBA results, drivers are at high risk of developing musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) due to prolonged sitting and poor posture, making ergonomic interventions essential. Regular breaks and specific stretches can help alleviate strain on the neck, lower back, shoulders, and other affected areas. Implementing health monitoring programs is also crucial, as 30% of drivers have pre-existing medical conditions such as high blood pressure, arthritis, and kidney problems. Regular check-ups can aid in the early detection and management of these conditions, ensuring that drivers remain fit for their demanding roles. Additionally, education and training on the impact of posture and long working hours on musculoskeletal health are equally important. Training programs that focus on correct posture, safe driving techniques, and exercises to strengthen key muscle groups could significantly reduce the risk of MSDs. Although no significant correlation between working hours and MSDs was found, it is important to recognize that long working hours may still contribute to fatigue and other health issues, highlighting the need for ongoing awareness and intervention strategies.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Abledu, J. K., Offei, E. B., & Abledu, G. K. (2014). Occupational and personal determinants of musculoskeletal disorders among urban taxi drivers in Ghana. *International Scholarly Research Notices*, 2014(1), 517259.
- Atlas, A. P., David, J. A. Z., Erese, R. R., Alejandrino, P. M. B., de Claro, M. C., & Agawa, R. A. (2006). Prevalence of low back pain among Jeepney drivers in metro manila: A descriptive study. *Philipp J Allied Health Sci*, 1, 56–57.
- Bardasi, E., & Wodon, Q. (2010). Working Long Hours and Having No Choice: Time Poverty in Guinea. *Feminist Economics*, 16(3), 45–78.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/13545701.2010.508574>
- Bontrup, C., Taylor, W. R., Fliesser, M., Visscher, R., Green, T., Wippert, P. M., & Zemp, R. (2019). Low back pain and its relationship with sitting behaviour among sedentary office workers. *Applied Ergonomics*, 81(January), 102894.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apergo.2019.102894>
- Cantin, V., Lavallière, M., Simoneau, M., & Teasdale, N. (2009). Mental workload when driving in a simulator: Effects of age and driving complexity. *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, 41(4), 763–771.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aap.2009.03.019>
- Caruso, C. C. (2014). Negative Impacts of Shiftwork and Long Work Hours. *Rehabilitation Nursing Journal*, 39(1).
https://journals.lww.com/rehabnursingjournal/fulltext/2014/01000/negative_impacts_of_shiftwork_and_long_work_hours.3.aspx
- Chand, A., & Bhasi, A. B. (2023). Anthropometric Assessment of Heavy-Duty Driver

- Postures Using RULA Method. *Transactions of the Indian National Academy of Engineering*, 8(4), 617–623.
- Coz, M. C., Flores, P. J., Hernandez, K. L., & Portus, A. J. (2015). An Ergonomic Study on the UP-Diliman Jeepney Driver's Workspace and Driving Conditions. *Procedia Manufacturing*, 3(Ahfe), 2597–2604. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.promfg.2015.07.584>
- Crawford, J. O. (2007). The Nordic musculoskeletal questionnaire. *Occupational Medicine*, 57(4), 300–301.
- Dhaiban, A. A. H. M., Bin Amro, A. M. A., & Amer, S. (2023). *Effects of Prolonged Sitting Posture on Neck and Shoulder Joints During Occupational Driving: Human Ergonomic Simulation Software*. 1879–1889. <https://doi.org/10.46254/an13.20230519>
- Erdinç, O., Hot, K., & Özkaya, M. (2008). Cross-cultural adaptation, validity and reliability of Cornell Musculoskeletal Discomfort Questionnaire (CMDQ). *Ergonomics*, 42(10), 1333–1349.
- Estember, R. D., & Espinosa, K. R. T. (2020). Ergonomic Interventions for the Transport Vehicle Drivers. *2020 IEEE 7th International Conference on Industrial Engineering and Applications (ICIEA)*, 330–334. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICIEA49774.2020.9102054>
- Hignett, S., & McAtamney, L. (2000). Rapid Entire Body Assessment (REBA). *Applied Ergonomics*, 31(2), 201–205. [https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/S0003-6870\(99\)00039-3](https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/S0003-6870(99)00039-3)
- Hita-Gutiérrez, M., Gómez-Galán, M., Díaz-Pérez, M., & Callejón-Ferre, Á.-J. (2020).

- An Overview of REBA Method Applications in the World [Una descripción general de las aplicaciones del método REBA en el mundo]. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(8), 1–22.
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85083418022&doi=10.3390%2Fijerph17082635&partnerID=40&md5=e3b03fb946e5d612402aaaab70f8beb0>
- Hoe, V. C. W., Urquhart, D. M., Kelsall, H. L., Zamri, E. N., & Sim, M. R. (2018). Ergonomic interventions for preventing work-related musculoskeletal disorders of the upper limb and neck among office workers. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*, 10.
- Mansfield, N., & Marshall, J. (2001). Symptoms of musculoskeletal disorders in stage rally drivers and co-drivers. *British Journal of Sports Medicine*, 35(5), 314.
- Mateo-Babiano, I., Recio, R. B., Ashmore, D. P., Guillen, M. D., & Gaspay, S. M. (2020). Formalising the jeepney industry in the Philippines – A confirmatory thematic analysis of key transitional issues. *Research in Transportation Economics*, 83. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.retrec.2020.100839>
- Max Banfield (2002). Posture Theory. Retrieved from <https://www.scribd.com/document/523430961/THE-IMPACT-OF-PHYSICAL-ERGONOMICS> on December 08,2024
- Mayasari, D., & Octaviani, D. (2017). Analysis of work posture using Rapid Entire Body Assessment (REBA) as the risk factor of work-related musculoskeletal disorders among bus drivers in Bandar Lampung City. *BMC Public Health*, 17(supp 6).
- Mingels, S. (2023). The Good, the Bad and the Ugly: Spinal Posture. *Journal ISSN*, 2766, 2276.

- Mohammadipour, F., Pourranjbar, M., Naderi, S., & Rafie, F. (2018). Work-related musculoskeletal disorders in Iranian office workers: prevalence and risk factors. *Journal of Medicine and Life*, 11(4), 328.
- Mokarami, H., Kalteh, H. O., & Tajpoor, A. (2017). Analysis of body postures for preventing musculoskeletal disorders among tractor drivers in Iran. *Journal of Health Sciences & Surveillance System*, 5(3), 100–106. https://jhsss.sums.ac.ir/article_42839.html
- Mozafari, A., Najafi, M., Vahedian, M., & Mohebi, S. (2014). Assessment of musculoskeletal disorders between lorry drivers in Qom, Iran. *Galen Medical Journal*, 3(3), e140–e140.
- MUGGLETON, J. M., ALLEN, R., & CHAPPELL, P. H. (1999). Hand and arm injuries associated with repetitive manual work in industry: a review of disorders, risk factors and preventive measures. *Ergonomics*, 42(5), 714–739. <https://doi.org/10.1080/001401399185405>
- Ogedengbe, T. S., Abiola, O. A., Ikumapayi, O. M., Afolalu, S. A., Musa, A. I., Ajayeoba, A. O., & Adeyi, T. A. (2022). Ergonomics Postural Risk Assessment and Observational Techniques in the 21st Century. *Procedia Computer Science*, 217, 1335–1344. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2022.12.331>
- Okunribido, O. O., Shimbles, S. J., Magnusson, M., & Pope, M. (2007). City bus driving and low back pain: A study of the exposures to posture demands, manual materials handling and whole-body vibration. *Applied Ergonomics*, 38(1), 29–38. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apergo.2006.01.006>
- Pickard, O., Burton, P., Yamada, H., Schram, B., Canetti, E. F. D., & Orr, R. (2022). Musculoskeletal Disorders Associated with Occupational Driving: A Systematic

- Review Spanning 2006–2021. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(11), 6837.
- Pradeepkumar, H., Sakthivel, G., & Shankar, S. (2020). Prevalence of work related musculoskeletal disorders among occupational bus drivers of Karnataka, South India. *Work*, 66(1), 73–84.
- Rinawati, S., Purnomo Adi, S., Tri Pangesti, L., Syahrotun Nisa, F., & Suryadi, I. (2023). Correlation between Work Duration and Work Posture with Musculoskeletal Disorders Symptoms in Interior Design Students at Campus Biru Surakarta. *E3S Web Conf.*, 448. <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202344803052>
- Serrano-Fernández, M.-J., Boada-Grau, J., Robert-Sentís, L., & Vigil-Colet, A. (2019). Predictive variables for musculoskeletal problems in professional drivers. *Journal of Transport & Health*, 14, 100576. <https://doi.org/10.6018/analesps.419911>
- Seva, R. R., Axalan, D. M., Rhea, A., & Landicho, P. (2011). Workplace Efficiency Improvement for Jeepney Drivers in Metro Manila. *Ergonomics Australia -Special Edition*, 1, 1–6. <https://www.ergonomics.org.au/documents/item/284>
- Srivastava, S., & Kiran, U. V. (2014). Work related musculoskeletal disorder on various body segments in taxi drivers. *International Journal of Science and Research*, 3(6), 1–8.
- Szeto, G. P. Y., & Lam, P. (2007). Work-related musculoskeletal disorders in urban bus drivers of Hong Kong. *Journal of Occupational Rehabilitation*, 17(2), 181–198. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10926-007-9070-7>
- Tucker, P. (2003). The impact of rest breaks upon accident risk, fatigue and performance: A review. *Work & Stress*, 17(2), 123–137.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/0267837031000155949>

Vaezipour, A., Oviedo-Trespalacios, O., Horswill, M., Rod, J. E., Andrews, N., Johnston, V., & Delhomme, P. (2022). Impact of chronic pain on driving behaviour: a systematic review. *Pain*, 163(3), e401–e416.

ANNEXES

TRANSMITTAL LETTERS

Republic of the Philippines
CEBU TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY
MOALBOAL CAMPUS
Poblacion West, Moalboal Cebu
Tel Nos. (032) 474-8196; 474-8104; 474-8383
Fax Nos. 474-8196; 474-8104; 474-8383
Website: <http://www.ctu.edu.ph>

February 2024

HON. CARMENCITA L. LUMIAN

Municipal Mayor
Municipality of Badian
Province of Cebu
6031

Ma'am:

Good day!

We, the Bachelor of Science in Industrial Engineering students at Cebu Technological University - Moalboal Campus, are currently conducting a study as a partial requirement of our degree. Our study, " **Assessment of Musculoskeletal Disorder for Jeepney Driver's; A Case of South Cebu,**" aims to assess the occupational challenges faced by Jeepney Drivers operating from Moalboal to Badian and vice versa, by gathering data through a survey questionnaire.

We understand that the cooperation of the drivers is essential to the success of this study. All information gathered will be kept confidential and the study's results will only be used for academic purposes.

We would be grateful if you could permit us to conduct the study to the Jeepney drivers of Badian. We assure you that we will comply with all the rules and regulations and will follow ethical principles in conducting our research.

We look forward to your favorable response. Thank you very much. Respectfully,

CHEVILYN ROSE G. GEMPEROSO
Researcher

JUVY DELA CRUZ BOLONGAITA
Researcher

ROGIE Y. MILMAO
Researcher

MESSIEH GRACE N. REUMA
Researcher

Recommending Approval

ENGR. JIRA MARIE MABANTO
Research Adviser

BENJAMIN D. RUBIN, CIE, MSIE
Dean, College of Engineering

CHARMAINE P. ANTECRISTO, Ph. D. TM
Campus Director

Approved by

HON. CARMENCITA L. LUMIAN
Municipal Mayor

HON. INOCENTES G. CABARON
Municipal Mayor

Republic of the Philippines
Province of Cebu
Municipality of Moalboal

OFFICE OF THE MUNICIPAL MAYOR

Telefax No. : (032)494-4172
moalboal@moalboal.gov.ph
Laguena St., Pob. West, Moalboal, Cebu

February 6, 2024

CHEVILYN ROSE G. GEMPEROSO
JUVY DELA CRUZ BOLNGAITA
ROGIE Y. MILMAO
MESSIEH GRACE N. REUMA
Students
CTU-Moalboal Campus
Moalboal, Cebu

RE: REQUEST TO CONDUCT A STUDY

Good day Greetings!

This is to acknowledge the receipt of your letter requesting approval on conducting a survey regarding on a feasibility study entitled "Assessment of Musculoskeletal Disorder for Jeepney Driver's, A case of South Cebu,".

In view of this, your request is hereby granted.

Done this 6th day of February, 2024 at Moalboal, Cebu.

INOCENTES G. CABARON
Municipal Mayor

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to be "Inocentes G. Cabaron".

QUESTIONNAIRES

Republic of the Philippines
CEBU TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY

Moalboal Campus

Poblacion West Moalboal, Cebu

Website: <http://www.ctu.edu.ph> E-mail: ctumalboalcampus@gmail.com

Tel.Nos.: (032) 474-8196; 474-8104; 474-8383

Fax Nos.: 474-8196; 474-8104; 474-8383

INFORMED CONSENT

INTRODUCTION

Thank you for considering participating in this study which will take part in Cebu Technological University Moalboal Campus- Moalboal Cebu. This information sheet outlines the purpose of the research study and describes your involvement and rights as a participant.

RESEARCH TITLE

This study entitled **“Assessment of Musculoskeletal Disorder for Jeepney Driver’s; A Case of South Cebu”**.

OBJECTIVES

This study assesses musculoskeletal disorders among South Cebu jeepney drivers by determining prevalence, identifying risk factors, evaluating driving conditions, analyzing ergonomics, providing intervention recommendations as basis for an action plan for improvement.

USE OF INFORMATION

The information that we will collect is intended for a research purpose only. The data gathered will be kept by the researchers.

ANONYMITY

We assure you that all the information from this study will be kept strictly confidential. Only our research group and adviser will have access to the gathered data. Your name will not be used and completely anonymous in any reports or publications resulting from this study.

If you are happy to take part in this study, please sign the consent sheet attached.

CERTIFICATE OF CONSENT

I have been invited to participate in the study. I have read all the information stated above. I consent voluntarily to be a participant in this study.

Name and Signature of Participant

Date

SURVEY FORM

Ngalan (Name):

Edad (Age):

Kinatawo (Gender): [] Male [] Female

Pinuy-anan (Address):

Nakasinati na ba kag sakit sa imong kalawasan samtang gabyahe?

[] NO

[] YES

Pila ka oras ka nagtrabaho sa usa ka adlaw?

[] 8 ka oras

[] 10 ka oras

[] 12 ug labaw pa

Sa usa ka adlaw ka pila ka mo byahe? _____ ka byahe

Pila ka minuto o oras ang imong pahuway matag humag byahe? _____ minuto/ oras

Naa ba moy laing gipamati daan sa ma sa?

[] High Blood

[] Stroke

[] Asthma

[] Diabetes

[] Heart Disease

[] Arthritis

Ug uban pa: _____

The diagram below shows the approximate position of the body parts referred to in the questionnaire. Please answer by marking the appropriate box.

	During the last work week how often did you experience ache, pain, discomfort in:				If you experienced ache, pain, discomfort, how uncomfortable was this?			If you experienced ache, pain, discomfort, did this interfere with your ability to work?		
	Never	1-2 times last week	3-4 times last week	Once every day	Several times every day	Slightly uncomfortable	Moderately uncomfortable	Very uncomfortable	Not at all	Slightly interfered
Neck	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Shoulder (Right) (Left)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Upper Back	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Upper Arm (Right) (Left)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Lower Back	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Forearm (Right) (Left)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Wrist (Right) (Left)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Hip/Buttocks	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Thigh (Right) (Left)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Knee (Right) (Left)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Lower Leg (Right) (Left)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

© Cornell University, 1994

Ang dayagram sa ubos nagpakita sa gibanabana nga posisyon sa mga parte sa lawas nga gitumong sa pangutana. Paliug tubaga pinaagi sa pagmarka sa angay nga kahon.

Sa maging semana sa trabaho, unsa ka subsob nga nasinati nimo ang kasakit, og pagkadili komportable sa:	Kung nakasinati ka og kasakit, og pagkadili komportable, unsa kini ka dili komportable?			Kung nakasinati ka og kasakit, og pagkadili komportable, unsa kini sa imong abilidad sa pagtrabaho?	
	1	2	3	Wala nakababag gamay	Nakababag Kaayo
Wala 1-2 ka 3-4 ka Kinasa gipadko besos sa baba sa kada makasinati maging maging adlaw adlaw semana semana	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Liog	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Abaga (Tuo) (Wala)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Buko-buko	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Bukton (Tuo) (Wala)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Hawak	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Kasway (Tuo) (Wala)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Pupolan (Tuo) (Wala)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Sampot	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Paa (Tuo) (Wala)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Tuhod (Tuo) (Wala)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Bagtak (Tuo) (Wala)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

© Cornell University, 1994

REBA Method

Find the full guide here:

Name: _____ Date: _____
 Workstation: _____

A. Neck, trunk and legs analysis

Step 1 Locate neck position

Neck in lateral flexion: Add +1
 Neck in axial rotation: Add +1

Score:

Step 2 Locate trunk position

Trunk in axial rotation: Add +1
 Trunk in lateral flexion: Add +1

Score:

Step 3 Legs

ADJUSTMENTS:
 Flexion is between 30° and 60°: Add +1
 Flexion is greater than 60°: Add +2

Legs are in monopodal support: +1

Score:

Step 4 Posture Score A

Using the values from steps 1 to 3, find the score in table A.

Score:

	Neck			Trunk			Legs					
	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3			
1	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4
2	2	3	4	5	3	4	5	6	4	5	6	7
3	3	4	5	6	4	5	6	7	5	6	7	8
4	4	5	6	7	5	6	7	8	6	7	8	9
5	5	6	7	8	6	7	8	9	7	8	9	10

Step 5 Effort and load score

- Load less than 5kg: 0
 - Load between 5kg and 10kg: +1
 - Load greater than 10kg: +2
 If shocks, violent posture change or high repetitiveness: Add +1

Score:

Step 6 Neck, trunk and legs score

Add the values from steps 4 to 5 to obtain the Neck, Trunk and Legs score corresponding to the rows in table C.

Score:

B. Shoulder, elbow and wrist analysis

Step 7 Locate shoulder position

Shoulder abducted: Add +1
 If the shoulder is supported or the person is leaning: Remove -1

Score:

Step 8 Locate elbow position

Score:

Step 9 Locate wrist position

If ulnar/radial wrist deviation: Add +1

Score:

Step 10 Posture Score B

Using the values from steps 7 to 9, find the score in table B.

Score:

	Shoulder		Elbow		Wrist	
	1	2	3	4	5	6
1	1	1	1	2	3	4
2	1	2	2	3	4	5
3	2	3	3	4	5	6
4	3	4	4	5	6	7
5	4	5	5	6	7	8
6	5	6	6	7	8	9

Step 11 Grip score

The hand hold is good with handles: 0
 The hand hold is not acceptable but possible: Add +1
 The hand hold is dangerous: Add +3

Score:

Step 12 Shoulder, elbow and wrist score

Add the values from steps 10 to 11 to obtain the Shoulder, Elbow and Wrist score corresponding to the columns in table C.

Score:

Step 13 Score C

Using the values from steps 6 and 12, find the score in table C.

Score:

Step 14 Activity score

If the posture is static (> 1min): Add +1
 If the posture is repeated more than 4 times per minute: Add +1
 If there is a quick and wide change of posture or unstable base: Add +1

Score:

REBA final score

Table C score + Activity score:

Score:

Score	Risk level
1	Negligible risk - no action required.
2-3	Low risk - change may be required.
4-7	Medium risk - vigilance, improvements to consider.
8-10	High risk - improvements needed.
>10	Very high risk - immediate response.

Check out your assessments and reduce your analysis time by 75% with NAWO Live www.nawo-solutions.com

CURRICULUM VITAE

CURRICULUM VITAE

I. PERSONAL BACKGROUND

Name: JUVY DELA CRUZ BOLONGAITA
Age: 22
Home Address: Poblacion East, Moalboal, Cebu
Date of Birth: November 1, 2002
Religion: MCGI
Email Address: bolongaitajuvy01@gmail.com
Contact Number: 09653666494

II. EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND

Tertiary: **Bachelor of Science in Industrial Engineering**
Cebu Technological University- Moalboal Campus
Poblacion East, Moalboal, Cebu

Secondary: **San Juan High School**
Pob. West, Moalboal, Cebu
S.Y. 2020-2021

Elementary: **Iglau-an Elementary School**
Murcia, Bacolod, Negros Occidental
S.Y. 2014-2015

CURRICULUM VITAE

I. PERSONAL BACKGROUND

Name: CHEVILYN ROSE G. GEMPEROSO
Age: 22
Home Address: Polo, Alcantara, Cebu
Date of Birth: August 04, 2002
Religion: Roman Catholic
Email Address: chevilynrosegemperoso@gmail.com
Contact Number: 09498066140

II. EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND

Tertiary: **Bachelor of Science in Industrial Engineering**
Cebu Technological University- Moalboal Campus
Poblacion East, Moalboal, Cebu

Secondary: **Saint Augustine Academy Inc.**
Pob. Alcantara, Cebu
S.Y 2020-2021

Elementary: **Polo Elementary School**
Polo, Alcantara, Cebu
S.Y 2014-2015

CURRICULUM VITAE

I. PERSONAL BACKGROUND

Name: MESSIEH GRACE N. REUMA
Age: 22
Home Address: Polo, Alcantara, Cebu
Date of Birth: March 24, 2002
Religion: Christian
Email Address: messiehgracereuma@gmail.com
Contact Number: 09324281633

II. EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND

Tertiary: **Bachelor of Science in Industrial Engineering**
Cebu Technological University- Moalboal Campus
Poblacion East, Moalboal, Cebu

Secondary: **Saint Augustine Academy Inc.**
Pob. Alcantara, Cebu
S.Y 2020-2021

Elementary: **Polo Elementary School**
Polo, Alcantara, Cebu
S.Y 2014-2015

CURRICULUM VITAE

I. PERSONAL BACKGROUND

Name: ROGIE Y. MILMAO
Age: 22
Home Address: Libo-o Ronda, Cebu
Date of Birth: September 01, 2002
Religion: Roman Catholic
Email Address: rmilmao010209@gmail.com
Contact Number: 09947564575

II. EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND

Tertiary: **Bachelor of Science in Industrial Engineering**
Cebu Technological University- Moalboal Campus
Poblacion East, Moalboal, Cebu

Secondary: **Ronda National High School**
Ronda, Cebu
S.Y 2020-2021

Elementary: **Tupas Elementary School**
Tupas, Ronda, Cebu
S.Y 2014-2015